

Oil drop face mask for sinus relief

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Abstract: Acute sinusitis is an infection caused by a virus that can lead to a congested or blocked nose, pain or pressure around your face, head, and eyes, loss of smell and taste, bad breath, ear pain, and headache. This common occurrence which has impacted about 14% of the general population happens due to the bacteria and viruses settling in the sinuses. Malaysia Statista reports that each person is expected to use 0.21 pieces of face mask in the year 2024 and is expected to be virus-killing, eco-friendly, and reusable. Through the idea and innovation of face masks, this study innovates sinus relief face masks. Sinus relief face masks are a combination of face masks with oil drops extracted from ingredients such as lemongrass, cinnamon, garlic, turmeric, ginger, and clove. This product aims to provide relief for those suffering from sinusitis while consolidating the elements of remediation and essential. With innovative features and differentiation, this product further bolsters growth potential. The extensive distribution reach enables broad customer access and high customer retention. This product aims for commercial success in the sinusitis relief market.

Keywords: face mask, oil drop, sinus relief

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sinusitis is an ailment that is no stranger to Malaysians. According to a report issued Ministry of Health (MOH) Malaysia sinusitis is considered a common health problem characterized by mucosal inflammation of the paranasal sinuses. In other words, sinusitis occurs when one's nasal cavities become inflamed and blocked with mucus. Ramiza (2022) added that Chronis rhinosinusitis affects 14% of the general population. Although sinus infection is considered common, this brings discomfort in people's daily lives.

Detroit Sinus Centre reported that inhaling steam can be another natural remedy that provides relief from sinusitis symptoms, by adding a few drops of essential oils can enhance the soothing benefits (Patricia, 2024). Therefore, the existence of the Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatment can be a convenient way to provide relief for those suffering from sinusitis. Extracting oil from natural ingredients such as cinnamon, garlic, turmeric, ginger, cloves, and lemongrass for aromatic purposes. The ingredients such as garlic, ginger, turmeric, cinnamon, and garlic are known for their anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant and some research discovered that their antimicrobial properties benefit also proved to help prevent nausea (Ajanaku, 2020). This is also supported by the studies on turmeric oil conducted by Prasad and Aggarwal (2022) found that the turmeric oil had antiviral effects on the respiratory tract and was proven effective against disorders of the respiratory tract.

The Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatment brought new insights for those bearing sinusitis and allergies by providing an alternative and innovative way. In a world often inundated with pharmaceutical solutions, the emergence of oil-drop nasal masks offers a refreshing alternative. These oils drop nasal masks, harnessing the therapeutic properties of oils, provide a natural and non-invasive method to alleviate symptoms and reduce dependency on traditional drugs. Gently diffusing essential oils directly into the nasal mask patch offers a holistic approach to wellness, promoting relaxation, easing discomfort, and enhancing overall well-being. With gentle yet effective benefits, oil drop nasal masks serve as a beacon of hope for those seeking to minimize their reliance on pharmaceuticals and embrace a more natural path to healing.

2. METHOD & MATERIAL

2.1 Materials

The basic ingredients prepared for oil drop nasal mask treatments are cinnamon, garlic, turmeric, ginger, cloves, and lemongrass.

2.2 Methodology

2.2.1 Preparation of Powdered Herbs

Figure 1: The ingredients are measured and prepared accordingly

Figure 2: All ingredients are grinded by using grinder for fine texture.

2.2.3 The Making of Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments

1. Prepare all ingredients cinnamon, garlic, turmeric, ginger, cloves, and lemongrass in fine texture.

Figure 3: Fine texture of ingredients.

2. The herbs are then being extracted until produce an oil

Figure 4: Fine texture of ingredients extracted to an oil.

3. FINDINGS

Based on the above method, it is proven that the ingredients turn to an oil drop and the oil can be used as a treatment as for oil drop nasal mask treatments. Below is the example of propose packaging:

Figure 5: The packaging includes an oil, face mask and patch.

Figure 5: The oil drop nasal mask treatment packaging.

4. DISCUSSION

The superiority of medical-grade masks in protecting against respiratory viruses is supported by evidence (Garcia Godoy et al., 2020). Specific improvised masks provide adequate protection when medical-grade masks are unavailable, according to the synthesized research. Such protection is preferable to no protection at all. Hence, developing these Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments will assist individuals battling sinus and allergy issues to overcome their apprehension of causing others discomfort. The concept of the Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments presented in this study aims to assist patients who suffer from sinus disease in the transition to a healthier and more convenient way of overcoming sinus disease that tends to sway the pain due to intolerance towards herbal smells. Thus, the prototype serves as a good starting point for the construction of innovation in healthcare terms. The Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments is capable of solving the issues with the overpowering smells from the herb, providing the patients with a soothing experience while consuming the Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments.

Since this study is developed only at the prototype stage, there are many opportunities for future research in this field. Further empirical research is needed to establish the efficacy of alternative Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments so that individuals are more adequately prepared to employ improvised nasal masks when required. In particular, further research is required to determine whether

an improvised Nasal mask with a filter containing therapeutic oil drop is more effective than herbs powder alone.

This study has several limitations. The literature encompassed in this review is constrained in terms of its scope, design, sample size, and population diversity. This study also included a prototype of the Oil Drop Nasal Mask Treatments, which have lower statistical power, and non-reviewed articles.

5. CONCLUSION

In this study, a nasal care face mask has been developed as an alternative method to alleviate sinus infections. The mask's oil drop contains a blend of herbal powders derived from natural ingredients known for their efficacy in treating sinusitis and allergy symptoms. This innovative approach aims to offer a therapeutic option for individuals suffering from sinusitis and allergies. Additionally, the nasal care face mask is cost-effective, indicating its potential to serve as an alternative treatment for sinusitis and allergies

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